

DESI Crosses the Half-Way Mark

Arjun Dey

Figure 1: Left: Current sky coverage of the DESI dark-time survey as of the end of October, showing that the survey is 54% complete. Right: Progress of the survey as measured by the number of extragalactic redshifts (25.9 million) and stellar spectra (9.3 million) measured so far. Credit: LBNL/DESI/A. Raichoor

The Dark Energy Spectroscopic Instrument (DESI) on the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope is currently running at a blistering pace: it measures 10 million extragalactic redshifts and 3.5 million stellar spectra every year! The 5-year DESI survey project, which began in May 2021, has now passed its half-way point (see Figure 1). On the night of 23 September 2023, the observing team, which included Amy Robertson, Luke Tyas, Tristan Fraser and Francesco Sinigaglia, marked this milestone by completing the 4965th dark-time tile (of 9929 in total) on the night of 23 September 2023. In short, despite the interruptions due to COVID-19, the Contreras Fire, and the cybersecurity incident, the DESI project is on track to complete its planned observations by mid-2026; in fact, the bright-time survey is already more than 75% complete, allowing the Collaboration to add an extra tiling of their footprint (and thus more than 20% more targets!) to the plan.

The DESI Collaboration has been hard at work analyzing the data and has already published nearly 180 papers. The early results from DESI are promising. The baryon acoustic oscillation signature is clearly detected in the early galaxy

clustering data (Moon et al. 2023; see Figure 2) and in the early quasar Lyman-alpha forest (see Figure 4 of Gordon et al. 2023). These will include results in measurements of unprecedented precision of the expansion history of the Universe to over a wide redshift range. The Collaboration expects to publish the cosmological results derived from the first year of DESI data in April 2024. The DESI Milky Way Survey is providing the largest ever collection of stellar spectra. It has also targeted stellar streams, a few dwarf galaxy companions of the Milky Way, and the Andromeda Galaxy. The millions of DESI spectra also enable searches and investigations of a wide variety of rare populations of astrophysically interesting sources (e.g., high-redshift QSOs, changing-look QSOs, coronal-line-emitting galaxies, very metal poor stars, rare white dwarfs, etc.).

DESI spectra are also likely to be an important complement to the Vera C. Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time. For example, DESI redshifts will be used for calibrating Rubin/LSST photometric redshifts and for providing (in combination with Rubin proper motions) 3-d space motions of

Figure 2: The baryon acoustic oscillation (BAO) peak at ~ 100 Mpc/h is easily detected in the two-point correlation function of the bright galaxy (BGS) and luminous red galaxy (LRG) samples as measured in the early data from DESI. The colored points show the measurements obtained with only 26% (BGS) and 12% (LRG) of the total survey area, and the dot-dashed curve shows models based on linear theory. The BAO feature is detected at 5(3)-sigma confidence with 1.7% (2.6%) precision in the LRG (BGS) samples (from [Moon et al. 2023](#)).

Milky Way stars. As a result, the DESI and the LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration have formed a joint team (the DESC-DESI Coordination Team) to explore how the two projects can support each other and to coordinate activities of common scientific interest.

As reported in *The Mirror* issue #5, the DESI Collaboration has made public an Early Data Release, which included spectra of nearly 2 million astronomical sources. The next data release is expected in late 2024 and will include spectra of all sources targeted during the first year of the DESI survey. We also anticipate the first cosmology science results, based on the first year data, to be released by this time.

DESI construction and operations is managed by the [Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory](#). This research is supported by the [U.S. Department of Energy](#), Office of Science, Office of High-Energy Physics, under Contract No. DE-AC02-05CH11231, and by the [National Energy Research Scientific Computing Center](#), a DOE Office of Science User Facility under the same contract. Additional

support for DESI is provided by the [U.S. National Science Foundation](#), Division of Astronomical Sciences under Contract No. AST-0950945 to the NSF's National Optical-Infrared Astronomy Research Laboratory; the [Science and Technology Facilities Council of the United Kingdom](#); the [Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation](#); the [Heising-Simons Foundation](#); the [French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission](#); the [National Council of Science and Technology of Mexico](#); the [Ministry of Science and Innovation of Spain](#), and by the [DESI Member Institutions](#). The DESI Collaboration is honored to be permitted to conduct astronomical research on Iolkam Du'ag (Kitt Peak), a mountain with particular significance to the [Tohono O'odham Nation](#).

References

- Gordon, C., et al. 2023, *JCAP*, 11, 045
- Moon, J., et al. 2023, *MNRAS*, 525, 5406